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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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INFLAMMAGING AND THE ALTERATIONS OF CHOROID PLEXUS

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Introduction: Many studies researching the aging process focused on the damage caused by T-cells in various tissues of the elderly, whereas the role of innate immunity stayed overlooked. Advent of the inflammaging concept shifted the focus to the relationship between organ changes occurring in the old age and cells of innate immune system. Our research focused on the inflammaging process in the central nervous system (CNS), more specifically, alterations found in choroid plexus (ChP).

Materials and methods: We obtained 30 ChP tissue samples which were distributed into 3 different age groups and then stained using hematoxylin-eosin (HE), anti-Iba1 antibody and Congo red stains. We looked into the number of Kolmer cells (special type of ChP macrophages) per unit of tissue surface (numerical density), amyloid deposits and vascular area in the ChP.

Results: Iba1 immunostaining clearly displayed oval and ramified shapes of Kolmer cells in all ChP samples, but despite slight increase in the number of Kolmer cells between different age groups, significant difference in the numerical density hasn't been found. Amyloid deposits visualized by Congo red staining, weren't observed in the ChP of younger patients but were detected in the samples of middle-aged (alongside middle-sized blood vessels) and elderly (alongside both middle- and small-sized blood vessels). A relation was found between a decrease in the ChP vascular area and older age groups.

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Conclusions: In conclusion, amyloid deposits and vascular area correlated with the aging process, whereas the number of Kolmer cells previously considered to be cellular markers of ChP inflammation, did not. Although further studies on role of innate immunity in ageing are needed, here presented parameters might shed light onto numerous age-related ailments of the CNS in the context of the novel view of inflammaging.

Keywords: Choroid plexus, Kolmer cells, Vascular density, Amyloid deposits, Age